

Appendix

Table 3. Quotations from thematic interviews by Deployment Management Capability (DMC) and stage of AI deployment.

DMC	Quotations by interviewees		
	Advanced	Middle	Early stage
Understanding the role of AI in digitalization and strategy (1-4)	"Digitalization is for us one of the 3 megatrends and AI is a strategic topic and strategic enabler. We launched the first AI application nearly ten years ago, and AI is present in all parts of the business. We focus on efficiency and ease of use. AI is a part of technology strategy, not company strategy."	"Digitalization for us is continuing the evolution which we started tens of years ago and AI is yet another tool for improving efficiency and quality of working." "We have built digitalization and established data governance and see AI as the most significant technology change and are increasing resources and investments in AI now." "Digitalization and AI are crucial for us, and we have built them into our company strategy. We are developing our culture to better support AI deployment."	"We are transforming our processes and IT systems to make them suitable for data (and AI) utilization. Now we are using some embedded AI in commercial applications as well as some point solutions. We are running pilots on language models to develop AI understanding and to learn about opportunities for adoption and deployment. AI is not built into the company strategy so far. We need to pay back the digital debt first."
Working the roadmap to deployment (5-6)	"There needs to be a clear connection how strategic goals are driven forward by using e.g., AI. We don't have to be the forerunner in everything; early adopter is OK. You must be prudent with e.g., cyber security and data sensitivity. Selecting in which business functions to apply AI is for the CIO, not for the board, to figure out."	"We go pragmatically "hand in hand" with our customers." "We need to make sure not to neglect these tools". "We are using AI in marketing and dynamic pricing and look actively for new applications." "Our approach is customers, not AI, even though AI is seen as a very important tool." "AI is not a strategic topic on corporate level, and we have distributed deployment responsibility to business level. Applications are related to processes, quality and physical safety." "The difficulty for the board is to foresee how this change will affect our company long-term."	"We don't have a vision for AI deployment, but we believe AI will in future play a role in increasing efficiency and speeding up our processes. AI experiments are not very high on our priorities, apart from limited LLMs. Supply chain management is a potential area once we get further on our path. In the near future AI will mainly come to our company through embedded features in commercial applications."
Setting the building blocks for business goals and results (7-10)	"We discuss AI in the board, but delineations, resources and objectives for deployment are decided between the CIO and the CEO. In the board we focus on corporate business goals and objectives and expect the CIO and the CTO to make sure that AI goals and objectives are linked to these. Naturally the CTO and the CIO have their own specific goals and objectives as well. We have attained clear measurable benefits in efficiency, and customer and employee satisfaction."	"In the corporate TMT we focus on resource allocation e.g., on IT budget level and want to make sure projects are based on high standards and practices. Special funding is provided if there is a justified proposal, and we want to know the outcome vs. objectives of the critical projects. Otherwise, we don't monitor the results on operative level." "We are increasing investments on AI and use value modeling when deciding go vs no go." "Our investments are based on best expected return; AI is not criteria as such. We have achieved clear measurable benefits." "We have a special development fund for bigger, and a fast lane fund for smaller trials. On top of our own experts, we have built a partner ecosystem. Objectives are set and followed up on business level." "Funding is not the problem, mindset and culture are. We follow and discuss the progress monthly."	"Our investments on AI are modest, except on LLM experiments and a few embedded point solutions. We have very limited AI resources currently due to other, higher priorities. Results from e.g., product quality application are significant. We see remarkable opportunities for improving our business through AI in the future. Metrics will naturally be based on business goals and objectives."
Solidifying the bedrock for continuous learning and development (11-13)	"Ease of use and making the solutions available for users globally are key enablers, so are data quality and availability. The attitude and eagerness of our people are also critical. We invest in lean and agile development and open interfaces to involve users and partners in	"We have long and solid history of math- and SW-based business but want to work closely with our customers and solve the global scaling, service and resource issues." "In the TMT we consider this mostly from resource perspective and we have	"We focus on data-related functions and activities. We rely on partners on AI and see it as one of the tools. AI cannot replace our products." "The most critical objective is operational continuity and hence architecture is important as a direction method. Third factor is data

the development process. Value proposal and how to sell it call for new and different competence.”

central and unit-level resources working together. Projects are often costly and take time but contribute to operative and efficiency improvements and synergy effects when coordinated.” “How to harness the technology for concrete benefits must be in strategy and on TMT agenda organized into operation and projects with objectives and follow up. This will differentiate winners from losers. People, their mindset, initiative, and innovation are crucial.”

“Are we doing enough, do we have enough of the right resources”.

availability and utilization, and we are getting there.” “We need to pay development debt first before being able to invest in AI in bigger scale. Data is perceived as an important asset, which needs to be managed.” “We upgrade the ERP first and move toward AI deployment once that is done.”

Ensuring leadership for strategic endurance and differentiation (14-16)

“We deliver and manage the data and the models by ourselves including legal and ethical follow up and actions.” “Low threshold, effective and agile organization, and risk tolerance are critical to be able to deliver. Confidence and trust come through delivered results.”

“Experimentation through MVPs and pilots, businesses are responsible, IT supports, a few deliveries have been made so far.” “Deliveries have been done by our partners so far.” “About 80 % of deliveries come from our partners.”

“We get AI in embedded deliveries.” “We have had some experiments but not deliveries or deployments so far.” “No AI deliveries yet.”
